

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

drsasikumarc@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port Cty	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārāyaṇīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुसंधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशविमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14646326>

“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”

Dr. Preeti R. Pujara¹

Abstract: The research paper titled “Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance” explores the multifaceted roles of women depicted in the ancient Sanskrit text, Amarushatak. Through an analysis of various shlokas, it delves into women’s roles as creators and destroyers of the universe, passionate lovers, dominant figures in lovemaking, and both submissive and bold individuals. The paper highlights Amaru’s nuanced portrayal of women, capturing their strength, vulnerability, and complexity. It concludes by suggesting that the depiction of women in Amarushatak remains relevant, showing parallels between ancient and modern perceptions of femininity and love.

Keywords: powerful rhetorician, socio-cultural milieu, dynamic portrayals, intricacies of love and longing, mixed rasas, Muktak Kavya, passionate lover, spiritual devotion and romantic longing, eroticism, interplay of power and vulnerability

Amaru, revered as a masterful poet and powerful rhetorician, occupies a distinctive position in Sanskrit literature. His creation, the Amarushataka, stands as an ideal example of Muktak Kavya. All 100 verses within this work delve into the realm of the art of lovemaking and explore diverse aspects of love. The predominant sentiment conveyed in most of his verses is Shringara, with an artistic display of eroticism.

Amaru’s compositions serve valuable resources for a deep understanding of poetic elements. Renowned rhetoricians such as

1. Assistant Professor, Dept. of Sanskrit, D.C.M. Arts & Commerce College, Viramgam, Ahmedabad

Mammata, Aandavardhana, and even Vamana frequently quote his verses while discussing various elements like *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Alamkara*, and meters, offering insights into the merits and demerits of poetic compositions. Moreover, his verses serve as exemplary illustrations for comprehending the different types of *Nayikas* described by Dhananjaya and Vishvanatha.

Aanandavardhana, the literary critic from the ninth century, extolled the poetic prowess of Amaruka in his seminal work ‘*Dhvanyaloka*’, proclaiming that “a single stanza of the poet Amaruka may provide the taste of love equal to what’s found in whole volumes.”

“ अमरुककवेरेकः श्लोकः प्रबन्धशतायते ।”Over the centuries, poets and critics have consistently turned to his verses as benchmarks and standards, using them to evaluate and assess other poetic works.

In the world of Sanskrit literature, the *Amarushataka* by poet Amaru stands as a vivid portrayal of women’s experiences, ranging from love and creation to destruction, submission, and dominance. Through its lyrical verses, the text captures the essence of human emotions with timeless quality. While the primary theme revolves around the intricacies of love and longing, the text offers rich insights into the roles and identities of women within the socio-cultural milieu of ancient India. Through evocative imagery, vivid narratives, and philosophical musings, the *Amarushatak* presents a wide spectrum of women’s experiences, ranging from dominance to submission. It shows women in ancient India were no different from today’s modern women. They were both bold and daring, at the same time they were meek and obedient.

Through a nuanced analysis of the dynamic portrayals of women in the *Amarushatak*, this research paper aims to disclose various roles of the women like woman as a lover, as an ideal wife, as a submissive typical Indian lady, as a powerful dynamic lady, as a warrior, as a supreme power- creator and destroyer of the universe and so on.

Amarushatak presents a wide spectrum of women’s experiences, ranging from dominance to submission. It shows Women in ancient India were no different from today’s modern women. They were both bold and daring, at the same time they were meek and obedient.

We can examine each role discussed above through the study of Amarushatak. This great book deals with the shlokas reflecting various facets of love and the art of love making.

Women as a creator and destroyer of the universe

The very first shloka, '*Mangala Charan*' of Amarushatak is unique where Goddess Ambika is evoked by the author, but at the same the shloka exhibits the beautiful picture of passionate lover. This blending of devotion to the goddess and the imagery of an ardent lover demonstrates Srinagar Rasa at its peak. It captures the essence of both spiritual devotion and romantic longing in a single verse. The shloka goes like this

ज्याकृष्टबद्धखटकामुखपाणिपृष्ठ-

प्रेङ्खन्नांशुचयसंवलितोम्बिकायाः ।

त्वां पातु मञ्जरितपल्लवकर्णपूर

लोभभ्रमद्भ्रमरविभ्रमभृत्कटाक्षः' ॥ (Durgaprasad and Panshikar 1)

The literal meaning we get from the shloka is -

May Ambika's side glance, made brighter by her dark pupils, merges with the radiant light emitting from her nails as she holds the bowstring in the '*Khatamukha*' pose. This combination forms an image akin to a blossoming flower earring adorning her ear, with a bee hovering around it greedily, seemingly offer the protection from harm.

This verse of Amaru is written in evocation of Goddess Ambika and her posture described here is a woman stretching a bow and ready to perish the evil forces of the world. Her eyes are grey in fury and ready to shoot the arrow to destroy evils. The literary meaning portrays goddess Ambika's heroic power. Here we can see role of women as a supreme power and '*Adishakti*' who has the power to create and even destroy the world.

But at the same time the verse has higher meaning beyond the literal meaning, Arjun Varmdev, the author of *Rasika Sanjivani*, has noted clearly in his commentary that the rasa indicated in the poem reaches to its highest pitch and the suggested meaning reflects truly felt love between man and woman.

Again '*Khatakamukah*' pose mentioned in shloka is also

suggestive, this pose is mentioned in science of archery. Bharata in 9th chapter of Nāṭyaśāstra discusses in detail about this posture especially in dance.

उत्क्षिप्तवक्रा तु यदानामिका सकनीयसी ।
 अस्यैव तु कपित्थस्य तदासौ खटकाभुखः ॥
 होत्रं हव्यं छत्रं प्रग्रहपरिकर्षणं व्यजनकं च
 आदर्शधारणं खण्डनं तथा पेषणं चैव ॥
 आयतदण्डग्रहणं मुक्ताप्रालम्बसङ्ग्रहं चैव ।
 स्रग्दामपुष्पमालावस्तान्तालम्बनं चैव ॥
 मन्थनशरावकर्षणपुष्पापचयप्रतोदकार्याणि
 अङ्कुशरज्ज्वाकर्षणस्त्रीदर्शनमेव कार्यं च ॥ (Ghosh 175)

It means this pose is used to represent sacrifice, oblation, umbrella, drawing up reins, fan, holding a mirror, drawing a pattern, powdering, taking up big sticks, arranging garland, taking up pearl necklace, gathering the ends of clothes, churning, drawing out arrows, plucking flowers, wielding a goad, drawing out string and looking at woman.

The posture of goddess in the opening verse indicates her dominant position in the art of love making. We come to understand that Goddess Ambika has the capacity to destroy invincible forces of evil just by her erotic dance and to capture the attention of her lover.

Reference to the darting the side glances of goddess while stretching the bow compared with a greedy bee. Rays releasing from gleaming nails compared with blossoming flowers set as an earring on the ears of goddess. (Suppleness of her hand) The whole description unveils the poet's desire to describe beauty and allure of Goddess that delights the lord Shiva. The picture of deep love between the lord shiva and the goddess is being imagined by the shloka.

In this verse, the idea of a lovelorn woman seeking a lover with her lustrous and darting eyes and dancing eyebrows is also seen. The goddess has shot an arrow to destroy evils and in the same way the lady love also seems to pierce her lover with the arrow of her love.

Here we can see Amaru's ability to use mixed rasas together i.e. Erotic and Heroic effortlessly. Very first shloka exhibits the role of women as a creator and destroyer of the world as well as ardent lover

who has the power to attract her beloved at the highest level.

Arjun varmadev, the commentator of Amarushataka also felt that Amaru's intention is very much clear to put female at the first position. He says though the Rasa in this shloka, Amaru wants to delineate erotic at its highest pitch indicating truly felt love between man and woman, and he also boldly suggests that eroticism in ancient India was not a taboo but the sacred union of man and woman. The poet's aim by putting goddess Ambika at first position in *Manglacharana* is nothing, but the predominance of woman in the ancient India and putting woman at first position is his tribute to female power and that is the reason he wrote first shloka on Ambika and second on Shiva.

यं रसं उपनिबद्धमेष कविः प्रवृत्तः स यद्यप्यकृत्स्निमानुरागस्त्रीपुंसपरस्परानुराग
कल्लोलितः परां कोटिमधिरोहति तथापि नायिकायाः प्राधान्यम् । तत्राप्राधान्यप्रकाशन
परश्चायमौचित्यात्कटाक्षमुख्यत्वेनाभीष्टदेवताशंसनश्लोकोऽपि प्रथमं लिखितः ।
(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 2)

Women as a passionate lover

Amaru has an art of showcasing vivid emotions of love and longing. Amaru's poetry is like a delicate dance of emotions, where love, longingness, and the raw essence of carnal desire are woven naturally.

The women in his verses are ready to sacrifice everything, even their lives, rather than be separated from their husbands. Their devotion knows no bounds, reaching levels of obsession.

There are numerous shlokas which portray the role of a woman as a passionate lover.

प्रस्थानं वल्यैः कृतं प्रिय सखैरस्रैरजस्रं गतं
धृत्वा न क्षणमास्थितं व्यवसितं चित्तेन गन्तुं पुरः ।
यातुं निश्चितचेतसि प्रियतमे सर्वैः समं प्रस्थितं
गन्तव्ये सति जीवित ! प्रिय सृहत्सार्थः किमुत्यज्यते ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 33)

Here in this shloka the beloved says that when her husband started moving on journey her bangles slipped from her hand, her patience broke and the stream of tears started flowing. Everything is

moving on and why I am where I am. why my life is sustained?

The following shloka also demonstrates how skillfully the heroine stops her husband from other talks and indulge in lovemaking.

After many days her beloved has come and he tells long stories about travel and for the heroine this was an obstacle to love making, so the heroine quickly went to the lamp and posing as if she was stung by the scorpion extinguished the lamp. Here there is a description of an ardent female lover who was unable to bear the separation of her hero, and who takes the initiative in love herself.

आयाते दयिते मनोरथशतैर्नीत्वा कथंचिद्दिनं
वैदग्ध्या पगमाज्जडे परिजने दीर्घा कथां कुर्वति ।
दष्टास्मीत्यभिधाय सत्वरपदं व्याधूय चीनांशुकं
तन्वङ्ग्या रतिकतारेण मनसा नीतः प्रदीपः शमम् ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 57)

There is another shloka in which the heroine shows her passionate love by kissing the beloved's face.

शून्यं वासगृहं विलोक्य शयनादुत्थाय किंचित्छनै
निद्राव्याजमुपागतस्य सुचिरं निर्वण्य पत्युर्मुखम् ।
विस्रब्धं परिचुम्ब्य जातपुलकामालोक्य गण्डस्थलीं
लज्जानम्रमुखी प्रियेण हसता बाला चिरं चुम्बिता ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 59-60)

The lady love quietly kissed the beloved who was lying on the bed pretending to be lying in the bed from someone in the house. The lover also kissed his lady love's face for a long time feeling the thrill.

Women's dominance in love making

Amaru's poetry portrays women as strong and assertive, maintaining their pride even in moments of weakness. Yet, their beloveds yearn for their closeness, pleading for them to set aside their ego and embrace intimacy. Amaru's skill lies in his depiction of this delicate dance between strength and surrender, where the pull of desire battles with the need for independence. In his poetry, the dominant presence of women in lovemaking is undeniable. Amaru's poetry reveals women as powerful figures, commanding love's reins.

In the following shloka we can see that lover is lying at the feet of his beloved and pleading her and asking her to leave her anger and

pride aside.

कठिनहृदये मुञ्च भ्रान्तिं व्यलीककथाश्रितां
पिशुनवचनैर्दुःखं नेतुं न युक्तमिमं जनम्
किमिदमथवा सत्यं मुग्धे त्वयाद्य विनिश्चितं
यदभिरुचितं तन्मे कृत्वा प्रिये सुखमास्यताम् ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 43)

In the subsequent verses, the lover says to her beloved that -look! your love is sitting at your door, writing your name and drawing your figure on the ground, your friends are crying continuously, their eyes are swollen, they left even food and look this parrot in the cage, who has given up laughter provoking prattle O' cruel hearted! now please leave your pride and ego.

The lover's words reveal his vulnerability and desperation to avoid further pain from his beloved's indifference. He longs for her kindness and understanding, willing to go to great lengths to please her and mend their relationship.

लिखन्नास्ते भूमि बहिरवनतः प्राणदयितो
निराहाराः सख्यः सततरुदितोच्छूननयनाः ।
परित्यक्तं सर्वे हसितपठितं पञ्जरशुकै
स्तवावस्था चेयं विसृज कठिने मानमधुना ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 11)

In all above shlokas we can observe despite their dominance, women yearn for acknowledgment and affection from their partners. Their strength compels male lovers to seek forgiveness, while their desire for deeper connection is palpable. Amaru expertly portrays this interplay of power and vulnerability, where even strong women seek validation. Through his verses, he captures the intricate dance of love, where pride and desire intertwine in a captivating symphony.

Women's dominance in the art of lovemaking is clearly visible in Amru's poem. Amru's poem unveils the timeless truth in the art of love making, it is women who hold the brush, painting the portrait of ecstasy and connection.

Submissive women

As discussed earlier in Amaru's poetry, women are often portrayed as strong and assertive, but there are also instances where

they are depicted as submissive to their husbands or lovers. women are depicted with a poignant blend of anger and innocence when betrayed by their husbands. They are ready to forgive their erring husbands, because they are dependent on them. Their sulking demeanour reveals the depth of their hurt and disappointment, yet beneath the facade lies a profound innocence and purity of heart. Despite the betrayal, these women possess a remarkable capacity for forgiveness, choosing to set aside their ego in the name of love. Their innocence shines through as they extend grace to their erring lovers, revealing a tender vulnerability that adds layers of complexity to their characters. Through Amaru's verses, the paradox of anger and forgiveness, of wounded pride and unyielding love, unfolds in a captivating exploration of human emotion.

In following shloka when she came to know about her lover's extra marital affair, she does not get furious rather curses her fate and accepts the reality. She as if allows her husband to indulge in such acts and utters with pain- "when your love which was so great has come to this pass, what pain shall I experience at the passing away of my life which is by nature so fragile?"

भवतु विदितं व्यर्थालापैरले प्रिय गम्यतां
तनुरपि न ते दोषोस्माकंविधिस्तु पराङ्गमुखः ।
तव यदि तथा रूढं प्रेम प्रपन्नमिमां दशां
प्रकृतितरले का नः पीडा गते हतजीविते ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 28)

In this shloka, the beloved decides to ignore her lover completely, vowing not to speak to him or acknowledge him in any way. However, when he appears before her or even casts a glance her way, her pride and ego melt away instantly, and she embraces him without any hesitation or complaint. This portrays the power of love to overcome pride and submissive nature of women in matters of love.

भ्रूभङ्गेरचितेऽपि दृष्टिरधिकं सोत्कन्तमुद्धीक्षते
रुद्धायामपि वाचि सस्मितमिदं दग्धाननं जायते ।
कार्कश्यं गमितेऽपि चेतसि तनू रोमाञ्चमालाम्बते
दृष्टे निर्वहणं भविष्यति कथं मानस्य तस्मिञ्जने ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 27)

Look at the following shloka with almost similar idea.

भ्रूभेदो गुणितश्चिरं नयनयोरभ्यस्तमामीलनम्
रोद्धुं शिक्षितमादरेण हसितं मौनेऽभियोगः कृतः ।
धैर्यं कर्तुमपि स्थिरीकृतमिदं चेतः कथंचिन्मया
बद्धो मानपरिग्रहे परिकरः सिद्धिस्तु दैवे स्थिता ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 67)

The shloka captures the inner conflict of the heroine as she tries to appear indifferent and proud in front of her beloved, but she fails to do so. She expresses that she has learned to control her expressions and emotions with great effort, such as raising her eyebrows, remaining silent, ignoring her beloved, and even restraining her smile. Despite her efforts, she finds it challenging to sustain this state without the blessing of God. This implies that without divine intervention, it is nearly impossible for her to maintain such a behavior.

Portrayal of Bold and courageous women

In Amaru's poem, we see portrayals of courageous and daring women. They fearlessly venture out to meet their lovers, disregarding any concerns about what others might think.

When asked if she is afraid to go alone at night to meet her lover, the lady boldly responds: "With Cupid by my side, armed with his love arrows, why should I fear?"

क्व प्रस्थितासि करभोरु ! घने निशीथे
प्राणाधिको वसति यत्र जनःप्रियो मे !
एकाकिनी बत कथं न बिभेषि बाले !
नन्वस्तिपुङ्खितशरो मदनः सहायः ॥ (Durgaprasad and Panshikar
54)

Again, in following shloka woman is portrayed as bold and brave

उरसि निहितस्तारो हारः कृता जघने घने
कलकलवती काञ्ची पादौ रणन्मणिनूपुरौ ।
प्रियमभिसरस्येवं मुग्धे तवमाहत डीण्डिमा
यदि किमधिकत्रासोत्कम्पं दिशः समुदीक्षसे ॥

(Durgaprasad and Panshikar 29)

As a bold lady moves confidently, even in the darkness of night, adorned with all her jewelry and finery. When a friend suggests she should go quietly and avoid wearing noisy ornaments like anklets that might give them away, the women in love pay no heed. Their

love is so strong that they overlook such reality and boldly pursue their desires, regardless of any potential consequences.

Amarushataka is a timeless portrayal of love through poetry. It captures love's essence deeply, going beyond traditional norms. Indeed, it celebrates love's purity and passion. Its verses vividly depict various emotions and moments of romance, creating a captivating world within each line. What is most noteworthy is the depiction of women in so many different roles. They are not depicted subservient to man, but they seem to be so much powerful and the driving force of the universe. The poem also presents the universal nature of human values. It seems to suggest that women in modern times are no different from their ancient counterparts. There is a dynamic interplay of roles we can witness here. They are bold, yet vulnerable. Women are dominating, yet they are submissive if the tide is against them. Woman in love is the most potent force transcending all physical boundaries. Overall, the Amarushataka continues to inspire and enchant readers with its portrayal of romantic love.

Works Cited

- Pandit, Durgaprasad and Vasudev Lakshman Shastri Panshikar, Editors.
Amarushatakam of Amruka with commentary of Arjun Varmdev. Nirnay
 sagar Press, 1916.
- Ghosh, Manmohan, translator, *Natyshastram of bharatmuni.* Asiatic society
 of Bengal Calcutta, 1951.
- Pandit, Durgaprasad and Vasudev Lakshman Shastri Panshikar, Editors.
Amarushatakam of Amruka with commentary of Arjun Varmdev. Nirnay
 sagar Press, 1916.

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,